

NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF AMINO ACIDS

Property	Products obtained													
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	XIII	XIV
R _f values (×100)														
(i) BAW	9.1	12.5	13.5	14.4	15.8	16.2	19.0	24.5	40.1	46.1	53.1	54.0	56.2	59.6
(ii) BAPW	37.2	41.6	42.0	43.8	45.3	46.4	50.4	52.6	66.8	70.2	71.2	72.5	73.1	74.8
Colours* with														
(i) Ninhydrin	V	BV	Gr	V	RV	Y	V	V	Br V	V	V	BV	Y	V
(ii) Isatin	P	dB	P	BP	P	B	P	PB	R	P	PB	PB	V	RV
Fluorescence in uv light	BW	W		BW	W	BW	BW	BW	BW	BW	BW	BW	—	BW
On spot in chromatography with amino acid	Arg	Asp		Ser	Gly	Pro	Glu	Threo	Tyr	Val	Try	Phe	—	Leu
Amino acid identified	Arg	Asp	—	Ser	Gly	Pro	Glu	Threo	Tyr	Val	Try	Phe	—	Leu
Amount (µg/g) of sample	7.2	0.5	—	1.7	7.2	8.6	9.2	5.3	8.2	6.5	7.6	9.8	—	9.7

*V=Violet, B=blue, R=red, P=pink, Gr=green, Br=brown, Y=yellow, W=white, dB=dull blue.

(4 : 1 : 1, v/v ; BAW) or 1-butanol-acetic acid-pyridine-water (15 : 3 : 10 : 12, v/v ; BAPW) as solvent systems. The authentic amino acids were run concurrently alongside of the concentrate as reference standards. The chromatogram was dried in air and then at 110°, examined under uv lamp⁶ (350 nm) for marking fluorescent spots and eluted with water for further characterisation. For locating and characterising the resulting products, ninhydrin (0.1 g/100 ml acetone), alloxan (0.2 g/100 ml acetone), isatin (0.2 g/100 ml acetone) and Folin's reagent (0.2% 1-2 naphthaquinone-4-sulphonate in 5% aqueous sodium carbonate) were used as chromogenic reagents. Twelve amino acids isolated were identified as arginine, glycine, serine, aspartic acid, glutamic acid, threonine, proline, tyrosine, tryptophan, valine, phenyl alanine and leucine. All these amino acids were isolated as their ninhydrin complexes by preparative-pc on Whatmann no. 3 paper and their relative yield was determined colorimetrically⁶ using a Systronics 106 spectrophotometer. The results are recorded in Table 1.

Antimicrobial activity: The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was measured using agar dilution method. The extract was subjected to a series of dilution (1 : 10, 1 : 20, 1 : 30, 1 : 40, 1 : 60, 1 : 80, 1 : 100, 1 : 120, 1 : 160) in test tubes having melted, cooled (45°) agar water bath. The agar dilutions were poured into plates. When the agar became solid the organisms to be tested, i.e. standard strains of *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *Ps. aeruginosa* and *P. mirabilis* were streaked on segments of agar surfaces and the plates were incubated. Effectiveness of the extract was indicated by failure of bacterial culture to grow which was compared with a control plate⁷. The results indicated that MIC of the extract for *E. coli* was 1 : 100 (10 mg ml⁻¹) and that for *Ps. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* 1 : 80 (12.5 mg ml⁻¹).

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A New Xanthone of *Hoppea fastigiata*

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IN continuation of our studies on plant pigments¹, systematic chemical investigation of *Hoppea fastigiata* Clarke (Gentianaceae)² has been undertaken. The plant is used for a variety of ailments and has apparently not been chemically investigated earlier. In this communication we report the isolation and characterisation of a new xanthone, having rare substitution pattern.

The air-dried powdered whole plants (aerial parts and roots) of *H. fastigiata* were extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and the concentrated extract was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution

of the column with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) gave a yellow solid which upon crystallisation from a mixture of petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°)–benzene (5:1) furnished yellow needles, m.p. 162–65°, $C_{18}H_{12}O_6$ ($[M^+]$ at m/z 288); λ_{max} (log ϵ) (EtOH) 250 (4.50), 315 (4.20) and 360 nm (3.75); ν_{max} (KBr) 3380br (bonded OH), 1660, 1625, 1605 and 1570 cm^{-1} (chelated α, β -unsaturated C=O), suggesting the presence of xanthone skeleton in **1**. The 1H nmr spectrum (90 MHz; $CDCl_3$) of the compound showed four *meta*-coupled doublets for four aromatic protons at δ 6.30 (1H, d, J 3 Hz), 6.60 (1H, d, J 3 Hz), 6.90 (1H, d, J 3 Hz) and 7.45 (1H, d, J 3 Hz) besides two singlets of three protons each at δ 3.70 and 3.85 due to two methoxyl groups. On complete methylation with $(CH_3)_2SO_4$, the xanthone (**1**) yielded a dimethyl derivative (**2**), m.p. 226°, $C_{17}H_{16}O_6$ ($[M^+]$ at m/z 316). Thus **1** must be a dihydroxydimethoxyxanthone. The appearance of four aromatic proton signals as four different *meta*-coupled doublets is suggestive of the fact that four oxygen functions (two methoxyl and two hydroxyl) are distributed in both the rings and are located in 1,3-positions; of these, the low field aromatic proton signal at δ 7.45 is consistent with a proton at C-8 having an oxygen substituent at C-7³, hence two oxygen functions in ring-B are at C-5 and C-7 positions. The presence of chelated hydroxyl necessitates the location of one of the hydroxyls at C-1. The parent xanthone was found to be insoluble in 5% Na_2CO_3 solution and its uv spectrum remains unaffected by addition of sodium acetate solution. This suggests that one of the methoxyl groups present in the compound must be at C-3⁴. Further, the second methoxyl group was assumed to be at C-5 as in the 1H nmr spectrum of the diacetate (**3**), C-8 proton signal is shifted downfield to δ 7.75 suggesting the presence of free OH group at C-7⁶. Thus, the new xanthone was characterised as 1,7-dihydroxy-3,5-dimethoxyxanthone (**1**). Finally, identity of the dimethyl derivative (**2**) as 1,3,5,7-tetramethoxyxanthone from comparison of physical constants and spectral data conclusively settles the above view.

- 1**; R = H
2; R = Me
3; R = Ac

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Lipid Constituents from *Artemisia annua*†

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ARTEMISIA annua (Compositae) is a Chinese medicinal plant. It has been introduced in India where it is growing successfully at CIMAP Regional Centre, Srinagar¹. During a large scale isolation of artemisinin, a promising antimalarial drug², it was also of interest to examine the other compounds. This has resulted in the isolation of four compounds, A, B, C and D.

The air-dried powdered leaves and stems of *A. annua* (50 kg) were extracted with n-hexane (6 × 180 dm³) and the resulting extract was concentrated to a syrup (1.1 kg). A portion of it (25 g) was chromatographed over silica gel (750 g), eluting with n-hexane with an increasing proportion of EtOAc in hexane. The fractions (200 ml each) were collected and monitored by tlc. Compound A (35 mg) was eluted in hexane, compound B (110 mg) in hexane–EtOAc (9:1), compound C (70 mg) in hexane–EtOAc (17:3) and compound D (40 mg) in hexane–EtOAc (19:1).

Compound A, m.p. 68°; ν_{max} 2960, 2920, 2855, 730, 720 (long chain), 1380, 1370 and 1180 cm^{-1} (isopropyl group)³; M^+ at m/z 450 corresponding to its molecular formula as $C_{32}H_{66}$. The generation of ions at m/z 435 ($[M-Me]^+$) and 420 ($[M-2Me]^+$) together with the ratio of abundances of $[M-Me]^+$ / $[M]^+$ indicated the compound to be branched having two methyl groups as substituents⁴. A close look at the mass spectrum of compound A indicated that the